

Dataset Paper

New Distributional Data of Butterflies in the Middle of the Mediterranean Basin: An Area Very Sensitive to Expected Climate Change

Stefano Scalercio

Consiglio per la Ricerca e la Sperimentazione in Agricoltura, Unità di Ricerca per la Selvicoltura in Ambiente Mediterraneo, Contrada Li Rocchi-Vermicelli, Rende, 87036 Cosenza, Italy

Correspondence should be addressed to Stefano Scalercio; stefano.scalercio@entecra.it

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Butterflies are known to be very sensitive to environmental changes. Species distribution is modified by climate warming with latitudinal and altitudinal range shifts, but also environmental perturbations modify abundance and species composition of communities. Changes can be detected and described when large datasets are available, but unfortunately only for few Mediterranean countries they were created. The butterfly fauna of the Mediterranean Basin is very sensitive to climate warming and there is an urgent need of large datasets to investigate and mitigate risks such as local extinctions or new pest outbreaks. The fauna of Calabria, the southernmost region of peninsular Italy, is composed also of European species having here their southern range. The aim of this dataset paper is to increase and update the knowledge of butterfly distribution in a region very sensitive to climate warming that can become an early-warning area.

1. Introduction

Large and updated datasets are fundamental tools for investigating the effects of climatic changes and environmental perturbations on biodiversity, mainly of sensitive taxa such as butterflies [1]. Butterflies are known to react to climate warming with latitudinal and altitudinal range shifts [2], but these changes are detectable only if distributional datasets are available. In Europe, some countries (Belgium, Finland, Germany, Ireland, The Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, and UK) adopted a standardized butterfly monitoring scheme from several years [3], but in the Mediterranean areas only the Catalan Butterfly Monitoring Scheme (<http://www.catalanbms.org/>) and the Suivi Temporel des Rhopalocères de France (<http://vigienature.mnhn.fr/page/suivi-temporel-des-rhopaloceres-de-france>) are working.

Models of species distribution in face of changes due to climate warming [4] are based on the actual distribution of species and future scenarios can be distorted when a model is based on few data. The southern range of the European distribution of butterflies is largely underinvestigated and

only few data are available for southern Italy, an area with a fauna very sensitive to climate changes [5]. In order to detect changes, it is important to investigate the distribution of both common and rare species, but bibliographic sources only rarely provide punctual and useful data of the former causing an important lack of information. Many data can be collected within private and public collections. This is an expensive procedure, but interesting data can be obtained on the past distribution of common species.

In Italy, the first attempt toward a knowledge of the distribution of the fauna at a national scale is represented by the Checklist of the Italian Fauna [6], with the distribution of species only generalized to large areas (North, South, Sardinia, and Sicily). Successively, the project CKmap supported the mapping of 10.000 species of animals at a national level in a UTM grid square [7]. Among them, the distribution of all butterflies species known for Italy was mapped and the localities georeferenced [8]. These localities were obtained from private and public collections, from private datasets, and from bibliographic resources, but very few were collected in the southern regions, where large territories are not explored.

FIGURE 1: Study area. It is located in the middle of the Mediterranean Basin. Territorial units are indicated as follows: 1: Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains; 2: Catena Costiera Mountains; 3: Sila Mountains; 4: Marchesato Area; 5: Serre Mountains; 6: Aspromonte Mountains; 7: Crati Valley; 8: Tyrrhenian Coast; 9: Ionian Coast.

The Calabria is the southernmost region of Italian Peninsula, located in the middle of the Mediterranean Basin. The regional fauna includes European species, having here their southern range limit, particularly sensitive to the risk of local extinctions as a consequence of the expected climate change. Papers devoted to the Calabrian fauna of Lepidoptera are very scarce and only in last few decades the studies were intensified [5, 9, 10]. Anyway, data are largely insufficient to study changes on a regional scale and data are strictly needed for detecting and mitigating risks such as local extinctions or new pest outbreaks.

The aim of this dataset paper is to provide new distributional data and georeferenced datasets useful for the study of dynamics linked to changes on large spatial and temporal scales in the Mediterranean Basin, a region very sensitive to climate changes that can become an early-warning area [5].

2. Methodology

In this dataset paper, all unpublished records of butterflies of the author are reported. Data were collected during the years 2005–2012, mainly in the Cosenza Province, covering all the seasons of butterflies' activity. Species are named according to the online database of the European Fauna (<http://www.faunaeur.org/>).

The localities were individuated by two toponyms: the first is the most precise and the second is the most easily recognizable on maps. Latitude and longitude were provided for all localities and grouped in territorial units with similar ecological, geomorphological, and biogeographic features in order to facilitate the individuation of areas that need further investigations. The territorial units individuated are nine [11]: Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains, Catena Costiera Mountains, Sila Mountains, Marchesato Area, Serre Mountains, Aspromonte Mountains, Crati Valley, Tyrrhenian Coast, and Ionian Coast (Figure 1). Data of localities are summarized in Table 1. Species lists were compiled as shown in Dataset Items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 (Tables).

3. Dataset Description

The dataset associated with this Dataset Paper consists of 5 items which are described as follows.

Dataset Item 1 (Table). Species list for the different localities of the Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains. Data presented in this table were based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of a butterfly species.

- Column 1:* Family
- Column 2:* Species
- Column 3:* Bosco Pollinello
- Column 4:* Campo Tenese
- Column 5:* Castrovillari
- Column 6:* Civita
- Column 7:* Cozzo del Pellegrino
- Column 8:* Fagosa
- Column 9:* Fiume Argentino
- Column 10:* La Calvia
- Column 11:* Monte Moschereto
- Column 12:* Monte Palanuda
- Column 13:* Monte Pollino
- Column 14:* Orsomarso
- Column 15:* Piani del Pollino
- Column 16:* Papisidero
- Column 17:* Petrosa
- Column 18:* Serra del Prete
- Column 19:* Serra Dolcedorme
- Column 20:* Timpa San Lorenzo

Dataset Item 2 (Table). Species list for the different localities of the Catena Costiera Mountains. Data presented in this table were based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of a butterfly species.

- Column 1:* Family
- Column 2:* Species
- Column 3:* Acquafredda

TABLE 1: Description of collecting localities.

Locality	Municipality (or nearest locality)	Administrative Province	Territorial Unit	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Latitude	Longitude
Cittanova	Cittanova	Reggio Calabria	Aspromonte Mountains	485	38°20'50"N	16°05'23"E
Monte Ulis	Cardeto	Reggio Calabria	Aspromonte Mountains	1045	38°05'39"N	15°45'21"E
Torrente Menta	Roccaforte del Greco	Reggio Calabria	Aspromonte Mountains	1400	38°07'13"N	15°54'24"E
Acquafredda	Aiello Calabro	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	800	39°06'44"N	16°11'21"E
Carolei	Carolei	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	480	39°14'43"N	16°13'22"E
Caselle	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	800	39°12'20"N	16°08'40"E
Contrada Manche	Grimaldi	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	625	39°07'54"N	16°13'21"E
Cozzo Caselle	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1080	39°12'57"N	16°05'11"E
Cozzo Cervello	Fuscaldo	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1200	39°24'00"N	16°04'03"E
Cozzo di Monte	Marano Principato	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	530	39°17'31"N	16°10'19"E
Fiume Jassa	Laurignano	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	300	39°16'18"N	16°14'56"E
Fiume Licetto	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	540	39°11'09"N	16°08'31"E
Fontana del Conte	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	985	39°10'48"N	16°11'33"E
Giardini del Signore	Aiello Calabro	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	150	39°06'35"N	16°07'17"E
Iassa	Malito	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	780	39°10'36"N	16°15'53"E
Laurignano	Laurignano	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	400	39°16'39"N	16°14'15"E
Mendicino	Mendicino	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	460	39°15'38"N	16°11'31"E
Monte Cocuzzo	Mendicino	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1540	39°13'06"N	16°07'50"E
Monte Serratore	Malito	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1190	39°11'19"N	16°14'00"E
Passo Crocetta	San Fili	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1000	39°19'17"N	16°06'44"E
Passo dello Scalone	Belvedere Marittimo	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	740	39°37'48"N	15°56'25"E
Petrarizzo	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	320	39°09'31"N	16°08'13"E
Ponte Nuovo	Belsito	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	270	39°09'18"N	16°17'38"E
Potame	Domanico	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	1000	39°11'04"N	16°11'48"E
Pucchiello	Lago	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	810	39°10'21"N	16°10'02"E
Rancilla	Grimaldi	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	590	39°07'07"N	16°13'14"E
San Fili	San Fili	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	560	39°20'11"N	16°08'15"E
Scannelle	Malito	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	890	39°10'24"N	16°15'27"E
Tessano	Dipignano	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	630	39°15'21"N	16°14'30"E
Torrente Brittone	Malito	Cosenza	Catena Costiera Mountains	700	39°09'52"N	16°14'58"E
Arvacata	Rende	Cosenza	Crati Valley	200	39°21'30"N	16°13'41"E
Contrada Salerno	Montalto Uffugo	Cosenza	Crati Valley	230	39°23'10"N	16°13'47"E
Cosenza	Cosenza	Cosenza	Crati Valley	250	39°17'27"N	16°15'22"E
Fiera di San Vito	Luzzi	Cosenza	Crati Valley	110	39°26'29"N	16°15'05"E
Lago di Tarsia	Tarsia	Cosenza	Crati Valley	60	39°36'45"N	16°18'24"E
Terranova da Sibari	Terranova da Sibari	Cosenza	Crati Valley	140	39°41'09"N	16°21'11"E
Brancaleone Marina	Brancaleone Marina	Reggio Calabria	Ionian Coast	2	37°58'10"N	16°06'23"E
Capo Colonna	Crotone	Crotone	Ionian Coast	15	39°01'33"N	17°12'09"E
Cariati	Cariati	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	30	39°29'58"N	16°56'35"E
Casino Feraudo	Terranova da Sibari	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	70	39°40'17"N	16°23'17"E
Caulonia	Caulonia	Reggio Calabria	Ionian Coast	110	38°23'50"N	16°24'55"E
Copanello	Stalleti	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	40	38°45'50"N	16°34'06"E

TABLE 1: Continued.

Locality	Municipality (or nearest locality)	Administrative Province	Territorial Unit	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Latitude	Longitude
Fiumara Trionto	Crosia	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	90	39°33'09"N	16°45'31"E
Gagliano	Catanzaro	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	370	38°55'18"N	16°33'21"E
Gattarella	Staletti	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	120	38°45'36"N	16°33'54"E
Macchia della Bura	Crosia	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	3	39°36'01"N	16°47'49"E
Mirto	Crosia	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	5	39°37'04"N	16°46'14"E
San Nicola	Caulonia	Reggio Calabria	Ionian Coast	150	38°22'55"N	16°24'53"E
Santa Maria del Mare Vetere	Staletti	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	190	38°45'23"N	16°33'46"E
Squillace	Squillace	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	100	38°06'00"N	15°45'30"E
Staletti	Staletti	Catanzaro	Ionian Coast	360	38°46'01"N	16°32'11"E
Strange	Calopezzati	Cosenza	Ionian Coast	65	39°33'35"N	16°45'02"E
Altilia	Altilia	Crotone	Marchesato Area	350	39°10'47"N	16°52'57"E
Cerenzia	Cerenzia	Crotone	Marchesato Area	630	39°14'42"N	16°47'13"E
Grave Grubbo	Verzino	Crotone	Marchesato Area	310	39°15'41"N	16°51'45"E
Presso Grotta del Palombaro	Caccuri	Crotone	Marchesato Area	115	39°14'36"N	16°50'30"E
San Mauro Marchesato	San Mauro Marchesato	Crotone	Marchesato Area	280	39°06'05"N	16°55'22"E
Santa Severina	Santa Severina	Crotone	Marchesato Area	285	39°08'48"N	16°54'49"E
Scandale	Scandale	Crotone	Marchesato Area	280	39°07'27"N	16°57'14"E
Bosco Pollinello	Castrovillari	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1800	39°53'50"N	16°10'38"E
Campo Tenese	Morano Calabro	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1000	39°52'07"N	16°04'22"E
Castrovillari	Castrovillari	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	330	39°48'49"N	16°12'35"E
Civita	Civita	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	400	39°49'46"N	16°18'50"E
Cozzo del Pellegrino	Orsomarso	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1850	39°44'34"N	16°01'01"E
Fagosa	San Lorenzo Bellizzi	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1600	39°53'38"N	16°14'07"E
Fiume Argentino	Orsomarso	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	180	39°47'38"N	15°55'56"E
La Calvia	San Donato di Ninea	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1760	39°44'38"N	16°01'46"E
Monte Moschereto	Civita	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	750	39°50'37"N	16°18'29"E
Monte Palanuda	Orsomarso	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1300	39°49'20"N	15°59'25"E
Monte Pollino	Morano Calabro	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	2200	39°54'22"N	16°11'13"E
Orsomarso	Orsomarso	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	120	39°47'53"N	15°54'40"E
Papasidero	Papasidero	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	190	39°52'23"N	15°54'38"E
Petrosa	Castrovillari	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	770	39°51'30"N	16°13'20"E
Piani del Pollino	Morano Calabro	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1850	39°54'46"N	16°12'37"E
Serra del Prete	Morano Calabro	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	2100	39°54'51"N	16°09'23"E
Serra Dolcedorme	Castrovillari	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	2267	39°53'39"N	16°12'57"E
Timpa di San Lorenzo	San Lorenzo Bellizzi	Cosenza	Pollino-Orsomarso Mountains	1200	39°55'02"N	16°17'45"E
Campoli	Caulonia	Reggio Calabria	Serre Mountains	450	38°26'39"N	16°23'55"E
Lacina	Brognaturo	Vibo Valentia	Serre Mountains	1000	38°34'59"N	16°23'32"E
Nardodipace	Nardodipace	Vibo Valentia	Serre Mountains	1000	38°27'47"N	16°12'11"E
San Nicola da Crissa	San Nicola da Crissa	Vibo Valentia	Serre Mountains	400	39°40'17"N	16°16'58"E
San Todaro	Nardodipace	Vibo Valentia	Serre Mountains	700	38°26'39"N	16°22'12"E

TABLE 1: Continued.

Locality	Municipality (or nearest locality)	Administrative Province	Territorial Unit	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Latitude	Longitude
Serra San Bruno	Serra San Bruno	Vibo Valentia	Serre Mountains	850	38°33'16"N	16°18'43"E
Ursini	Caulonia	Reggio Calabria	Serre Mountains	420	38°24'49"N	16°24'04"E
Acri	Acri	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	734	39°29'50"N	16°22'02"E
Bocca di Piazza	Parenti	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1250	39°09'44"N	16°28'46"E
Cicciardi	Pedivigliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	680	39°07'07"N	16°19'01"E
Col di Vura	Rossano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1020	39°32'20"N	16°34'54"E
Colle dei Lupi	Rogliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1050	39°11'27"N	16°25'23"
Colle dell'Esca	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1630	39°25'09"N	16°36'03"E
Confluenza Savuto-Bisirico	Scigliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	180	39°06'48"N	16°15'42"E
Coraci	Colosimi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	780	39°06'53"N	16°22'41"E
Cozzo del Pupatolo	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1550	39°25'16"N	16°35'22"E
Cupone	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1160	39°23'12"N	16°33'05"E
Favali	Parenti	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1215	39°09'19"N	16°27'05"E
Fossia	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1300	39°23'43"N	16°35'56"E
Fosso Cucolo	Donnici Inferiore	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	550	39°14'13"N	16°17'50"E
Lago Ariamacina	Camigliatello Silano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1320	39°19'54"N	16°33'11"E
Lago Arvo	Lorica	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1290	39°14'54"N	16°31'56"E
Lago Cecita	Camigliatello Silano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1120	39°22'03"N	16°30'17"E
Lago Savuto	Parenti	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1160	39°10'40"N	16°29'19"E
Macrocioli	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1150	39°25'24"N	16°36'58"E
Marzi	Marzi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	570	39°10'22"N	16°18'22"E
Mascari	Colosimi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	910	39°06'50"N	16°24'09"E
Mauritanella	Santo Stefano di Rogliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1000	39°11'37"N	16°22'54"E
Monte Colonnina	Caloveto	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	530	39°29'52"N	16°44'50"E
Monte Gabriele	Rogliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	750	39°10'19"N	16°21'07"E
Monte Scuro	Spezzano della Sila	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1620	39°20'06"N	16°23'56"E
Morachi	Bianchi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	790	39°05'40"N	16°24'49"E
Piano del Barone	Acri	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1100	39°27'47"N	16°28'32"E
Pianoro di Macchialonga	Spezzano della Sila	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1540	39°22'22"N	16°35'37"E
Pietra di Pesco	Rogliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	960	39°10'56"N	16°22'08"E
Pittarella	Pedivigliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	505	39°06'29"N	16°17'53"E
Ponte della Castagna	Bianchi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	740	39°03'56"N	16°25'15"E
Ponte della Tavoliera	Marzi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	550	39°10'06"N	16°22'29"E
Saliano	Rogliano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	935	39°10'50"N	16°25'50"E
San Leo	Parenti	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	730	39°09'49"N	16°25'14"E
Sant'Angelo	Panettieri	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	890	39°04'02"N	16°27'14"E
Serra Castagna Versante Sud	Longobucco	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1230	39°29'53"N	16°32'24"E
Soveria Mannelli	Soveria Mannelli	Catanzaro	Sila Mountains	900	39°05'20"N	16°23'04"E
Torrente Savucchia	Carpanzano	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	590	39°08'57"N	16°18'02"E
Trenta	Trenta	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	400	39°16'48"N	16°17'39"E

TABLE I: Continued.

Locality	Municipality (or nearest locality)	Administrative Province	Territorial Unit	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	Latitude	Longitude
Trenta Coste	Acri	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1000	39°29'18"N	16°30'46"E
Valle Capra	Spezzano della Sila	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	1180	39°21'06"N	16°29'20"E
Vallone Prunillo	Bianchi	Cosenza	Sila Mountains	780	39°03'50"N	16°25'47"E
Amantea	Amantea	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	2	39°08'13"N	16°04'03"E
Cessaniti	Cessaniti	Vibo Valentia	Tyrrhenian Coast	350	38°40'12"N	16°00'52"E
Cittadella del Capo	Bonifati	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	15	39°33'11"N	15°52'45"E
Fiume Abatemarco	Verbicaro	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	90	39°44'59"N	15°51'32"E
Foce Fiume Savuto	Nocera Terinese	Catanzaro	Tyrrhenian Coast	2	39°01'55"N	16°06'00"E
Monte Pellegrino	Amantea	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	250	39°06'12"N	16°05'20"E
Paola	Paola	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	160	39°21'57"N	16°02'39"E
Praia a Mare	Praia a Mare	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	10	39°53'11"N	15°47'02"E
Sanginetto	Bonifati	Cosenza	Tyrrhenian Coast	50	39°34'49"N	15°52'15"E
Tropea	Tropea	Vibo Valentia	Tyrrhenian Coast	50	38°40'37"N	15°53'48"E
Valle Ruffa	Spilinga	Vibo Valentia	Tyrrhenian Coast	300	38°38'00"N	15°54'08"E

Column 4: Carolei
Column 5: Caselle
Column 6: Contrada Manche
Column 7: Cozzo Caselle
Column 8: Cozzo Cervello
Column 9: Cozzo di Monte
Column 10: Fiume Jassa
Column 11: Fiume Licetto
Column 12: Fontana del Conte
Column 13: Giardini del Signore
Column 14: Iassa
Column 15: Laurignano
Column 16: Mendicino
Column 17: Monte Cocuzzo
Column 18: Monte Serratore
Column 19: Passo Crocetta
Column 20: Passo dello Scalone
Column 21: Petrarizzo
Column 22: Ponte Nuovo
Column 23: Potame
Column 24: Pucchiello
Column 25: Rancilla
Column 26: San Fili
Column 27: Scannelle
Column 28: Tessano
Column 29: Torrente Brittone

Dataset Item 3 (Table). Species list for the different localities of the Sila Mountains. Data presented in this table were based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of a butterfly species.

Column 1: Family
Column 2: Species
Column 3: Acri
 ⋮
Column 41: Trenta Coste
Column 42: Valle Capra
Column 43: Vallone Prunillo

Dataset Item 4 (Table). Species list for the different localities of the Tyrrhenian Coast (Amantea, Cessaniti, Cittadella del Capo, Fiume Abatemarco, Foce Fiume Savuto, Monte Pellegrino, Paola, Praia a Mare, Sangineto, Valle Ruffa, and Tropea) and Ionian Coast (Brancaleone Marina, Capo Colonna, Cariati, Casino Feraudo, Caulonia, Copanello, Fiumara Trionto, Gagliano, Gattarella, Macchia della Bura, Mirto, San Nicola, Santa Maria del Mare Vetere, Squillace, Staletti, and Strange). Data presented in this table were based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of a butterfly species.

Column 1: Family
Column 2: Species
Column 3: Amantea
Column 4: Cessaniti
Column 5: Cittadella del Capo
Column 6: Fiume Abatemarco
Column 7: Foce Fiume Savuto
Column 8: Monte Pellegrino
Column 9: Paola
Column 10: Praia a Mare
Column 11: Sangineto
Column 12: Valle Ruffa
Column 13: Tropea
Column 14: Brancaleone Marina
Column 15: Capo Colonna
Column 16: Cariati
Column 17: Casino Feraudo
Column 18: Caulonia
Column 19: Copanello
Column 20: Fiumara Trionto
Column 21: Gagliano
Column 22: Gattarella
Column 23: Macchia della Bura
Column 24: Mirto
Column 25: San Nicola
Column 26: Santa Maria del Mare Vetere
Column 27: Squillace
Column 28: Staletti
Column 29: Strange

Dataset Item 5 (Table). Species list for the different localities of Marchesato Area (Altilia, Cerenzia, Presso Grotta del Palombaro, San Mauro Marchesato, Santa Severina, Scandale, and Grave Grubbo), Crati Valley (Arcavacata, Contrada Salerno, Cosenza, Fiera di San Vito, Lago di Tarsia, and Terranova da Sibari), Serre Mountains (Campoli, Lacina, Nardodipace, San Todaro, San Nicola da Crissa, Serra San Bruno, and Ursini), and Aspromonte Mountains (Cittanova, Monte Ullis, and Torrente Menta). Data presented in this table were based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of a butterfly species.

Column 1: Family
Column 2: Species
Column 3: Altilia
Column 4: Cerenzia
Column 5: Presso Grotta del Palombaro
Column 6: San Mauro Marchesato
Column 7: Santa Severina
Column 8: Scandale
Column 9: Grave Grubbo

Column 10: Arcavacata
 Column 11: Contrada Salerni
 Column 12: Cosenza
 Column 13: Fiera di San Vito
 Column 14: Lago di Tarsia
 Column 15: Terranova da Sibari
 Column 16: Campoli
 Column 17: Lacina
 Column 18: Nardodipace
 Column 19: San Todaro
 Column 20: San Nicola da Crissa
 Column 21: Serra San Bruno
 Column 22: Ursini
 Column 23: Cittanova
 Column 24: Monte Ulis
 Column 25: Torrente Menta

4. Concluding Remarks

This Dataset Paper strongly increases the knowledge on the butterfly fauna of Calabria, the southernmost region of the Italian Peninsula, composed of 135 species [10]. New distributional data for 116 species of butterflies are provided, the 86% of the whole regional fauna. The presence of species was recorded for 136 localities, for a total of 815 new distributional records. To date, the most data rich paper for this region provided 745 distributional records for 44 localities [9].

There is a heterogeneous distribution of sampled localities on the regional territory. In fact, Sila and Catena Costiera Mountains appear to be better sampled than others.

Dataset Availability

The dataset associated with this Dataset Paper is dedicated to the public domain using the CC0 waiver and is available at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/176471/dataset>.

Disclosure

The data presented here were collected by the author during several field trips and during several research activities of the author from 2005 to 2012. The data are unpublished and represent an important implementation of the knowledge on the butterfly fauna of Italy.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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